

ON THE QUESTION OF OBESITY IN CHILDREN AND ADOLESCENTS

Suleymanova S.F.,

PhD, Associate Professor

Scientific Research Institute of Medical Prevention named after V.Y.Akhundov, Head of Laboratory,

Afandiyeva S.F.,

Scientific Research Institute of Medical Prevention named after V.Y.Akhundov, Head of Laboratory,

Guseynova S.B.,

Scientific Research Institute of Medical Prevention named after V.Y.Akhundov, Senior Researcher

Babayeva A.Kh.

Scientific Research Institute of Medical Prevention named after V.Y.Akhundov, Researcher

Abstract

The new WHO European Regional Obesity Report 2022, published on 3 May by the WHO Regional Office for Europe, reveals that overweight and obesity rates have reached epidemic proportions across the Region and are still escalating, with none of the 53 Member States of the Region currently on track to meet the WHO Global Noncommunicable Disease (NCD) target of halting the rise of obesity by 2025.

The report launched at a press event on 3 May and presented at the European Congress on Obesity, reveals that in the European Region, 59% of adults and almost 1 in 3 children (29% of boys and 27% of girls) are overweight or living with obesity. Obesity prevalence for adults in the European Region is higher than in any other WHO region except for the Americas.

Overweight and obesity are among the leading causes of death and disability in the European Region, with recent estimates suggesting they cause more than 1.2 million deaths annually, corresponding to more than 13% of total mortality in the Region [1,4].

Obesity increases the risk for many NCDs, including cancers, cardiovascular diseases, type 2 diabetes mellitus and chronic respiratory diseases. For example, obesity is considered a cause of at least 13 different types of cancer, and is likely to be directly responsible for at least 200 000 new cancer cases annually across the Region, with this figure set to rise further in the coming years. Overweight and obesity are also the leading risk factor for disability, causing 7% of total years lived with disability in the Region.

Keywords: obesity in children and adolescents, rational nutrition, menu

Obesity is a disease – not only a risk factor.

Over the past few decades, there has been a tendency towards a rapid increase in the number of obese children and adolescents worldwide [5]. The number of obese children and adolescents aged 5 to 19 years increased from 11 million in 1975 to 124 million in 2016, and 213 million were overweight in 2016 [3,4].

Over the past few decades, there has been a trend towards a rapid increase in the number of children and adolescents with obesity around the world. The number of obese children and adolescents aged 5 to 19 has increased almost 20-fold since 1975. To find better solutions to this problem, quality data is needed [2,5].

The WHO European Office for the Prevention and Control of Noncommunicable Diseases (NCD Office) is organizing a webinar to present a new Childhood Obesity Surveillance Initiative (COSI) report. Its findings are based on the latest WHO data gathered in 2018–2020 in 33 countries. In total, almost 411 000 children aged 6–9 years were measured. Starting this 2023 year, Azerbaijan also joins in reporting on this issue.

This initiative is made possible through a vital collaboration between WHO/Europe and research and public health institutions across the European Region.

To contribute to the fight against this problem, we conducted a study. The purpose of these studies was to

compile a menu for school-age children, taking into account not only age, energy costs, but climatic living conditions and national characteristics of cuisine.

The research was conducted based on personal data from schoolchildren in three districts of the city of Baku. The obtained data were statistically processed by the Tietjen-Moore and Student's T-test methods and were found to be reliable.

Our research was based on the principles of rational nutrition. Rational nutrition is a balanced diet, compiled taking into account gender, age, health status, lifestyle, the nature of work and professional activity of a person, and the climatic conditions of his residence.

What does a balanced diet include?

- Lean meat (beef, mutton, rabbit) no more than 2 times a week. A single serving in finished form is 60-80 g.

- Poultry 5 times a week. A single serving in finished form is 60-80 g.

- Fish/seafood 2-3 servings per week. A single serving in finished form is 60-80 g.

- Eggs, depending on concomitant diseases, from 3 to 6 yolks per week. Protein every day.

- Olive or other vegetable oil - with each main meal, 2 times a day. Single serving 5-8 g.

- Vegetables 3-4 times a day. Raw, stew, in soup, etc.

- Fruits/dried fruits 1-2 times a day. Fruit up to 200 g or 50 g of dried fruit.

➤ Bread/cereals/side dishes 3-4 rubles/day. One serving of bread 30-40 g, ready-made side dish - 80 g. Choose buckwheat, brown/wild rice, durum wheat pasta, quinoa, bulgur and other healthy complex carbohydrates.

➤ Legumes 1 serving per week. Single serving in finished form - 80 g.

➤ Unroasted nuts 1 serving per day. Single serving no more than 25 g.

The nutrition of a schoolchild, both at 7 years old and at 12 years old, should be correct and balanced. In order to maximally supply the body with all the necessary substances, several nuances should be taken into account. Throughout the day, the child should receive the amount of calories that the body expends. Food should be varied. In addition, the diet is balanced. It is imperative to take into account the individual characteristics of the body. Animal protein entering the body should be at least 50% of the total amount. There are 3 times more carbohydrates than proteins and fats. The maximum amount of fast carbohydrates (sweets, cakes) for each day is 15% of the total amount. Be sure to develop a diet to eat regularly. Mandatory consumption of potatoes and cereals. Several times a calendar week, fish should be present on the child's table. Red meat is present in the diet at least 2 times. You should dilute your food with legumes several times. Your child should eat fruits and vegetables every day. Milk-based products should be present every day. It is advisable to add food additives as rarely as possible. For schoolchildren, especially primary school children, sweets should not replace normal food. Products that should be strictly dosed or excluded as much as possible: white bread, if it is not made from durum wheat, and sugar, which contribute to rapid weight gain. Exclude any products with industrial food additives, palm oil, margarine, fruits, out-of-season vegetables, soda, caffeine (as well as products based on it), ketchup, mayonnaise, store-bought sauce. Avoid highly spicy or sour foods; food products in fast food outlets; sausages, especially raw smoked ones. Exclude mushrooms of unknown origin; packaged juices; lollipops, chewing gum, as well as any discounted products whose expiration date is running out.

When building a child's routine, attention is paid to the shift when he attends school. For the first shift: you should have breakfast from 7-8. Light snack in the educational institution from 10-11. Lunch, no matter where, from 13-14. Dinner from 19-20. For the second shift: breakfast from 8-9. Lunch - at home before school from 12-13. Light snack in the educational institution from 16-17. Dinner from 19-20. About 55-65% of daily calories come from the first two meals - breakfast and lunch. Dinner, at the latest two hours before bedtime. Throughout the day, regardless of main meals, it is allowed to eat fruits or fresh vegetables. Snacks are best made from homemade products.

Before you make a plan, you need to understand the correct menu design. Breakfast should consist of 250-350g of main dishes, for example, porridge, omelet, and cheeses. Drinks can include tea, cocoa, and freshly squeezed juices. Approximate quantity 150-

250ml. Lunch consists of a vegetable salad or other snack up to 100g, soup 250-350ml, main courses 250-300g, drinks 150-250ml. A snack or afternoon snack can consist of dairy products or fruit, homemade cakes are good. Pastries and fruits up to 100-150g, milk drinks or dried fruit compote up to 250ml. Dinner should include up to 350g of solid food and up to 250ml of drinks. Daily bread consumption: durum wheat up to 150-200g, rye up to 100g. It is necessary to monitor the child's condition, and take into account the lifestyle. For example, an active child or one who plays sports will consume more food than a passive one and this will not affect his general condition. It is necessary to teach a child to eat normally from an early age, and it is better if this is a common habit for the whole family. Therefore, in connection with the above, we can draw the following conclusions:

➤ Nutrition should be balanced individually in accordance with the energy expenditure of each child
2. Nutrition should be balanced; complete and varied (include proteins, fats, and carbohydrates in accordance with the nutritional formula).

➤ Particular attention should be paid to the protein component of food. Immunoglobulins (immune system proteins) are formed from amino acids.

➤ It is better to eat at home according to your diet.

➤ It is advisable to take additional vitamins and minerals not randomly, but only if there is a specifically laboratory-determined deficiency when prescribed by a doctor.

➤ Avoid overeating. The finished portion should not exceed 200-300 g (depending on the age of the child and the amount of energy expended).

➤ Monitor your drinking regime. Drink approximately 1-1.5 liters of water per day.

➤ Strictly limit your intake of sugary carbonated drinks.

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